

Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS)

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Portions of this document echo sections of a whitepaper created for participants in the first rulebook development workshop.⁸ Other portions contain placeholder text that will be further developed during the technical pilot of the OAEBUDT-IDS. Purple highlighted sections will be developed in 2024 with community consultation and direct involvement from the Board of Trustees and its Membership and Sustainability Committee. Green sections will be directly informed by technical pilots and are expected to be drafted late 2024 / early 2025. Standard contractual clauses and legal agreements referenced at the end of the document will be drafted as based on lessons learned during the technical pilot.

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The key terms in this document are referenced in derivative [OAEBUDT legal agreements](#) are intentionally bolded. E.g. **Data Provider, Data Recipient, OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**.

² <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/ids-ram/>

³ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDSA-Rulebook>

⁴ <https://www.sitra.fi/en/publications/rulebook-for-a-fair-data-economy/>

⁵ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/idsa-rulebook/idsa-rulebook/6_legal_dimensions

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/8319929>

⁷ Affiliations at time of engagement

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/8345034>

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SECTION I | OAEBUDT-IDS PARTICIPANT RULEBOOK OVERVIEW

This section begins by describing the purpose, scope and intended audience for this document. Format and organization notes are followed by a short description of the OA Book Usage Data Trust's International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS).

Rulebook Purpose & Scope

This document outlines the governance, function, and principles that guide the operations of the OA Book Usage Data Trust and the International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) data intermediation service it coordinates for book usage data stakeholders. A "Data Space" embodies the idea of sharing data without centralized storage, to ensure the data remains at its original source and only shared as intended. This rulebook informs derivative legal agreements and service contracts for OAEBUDT-IDS participation by summarizing the community-developed principles, processes, and requirements that ensure trust and neutrality in the OAEBUDT-IDS as it services the diverse public and private stakeholders who rely on book usage data.

This Rulebook is one of many pieces of documentation for the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) effort. Individuals seeking additional information should review www.oabookusage.org and the [recommended readings](#) noted at the end of this document.

OAEBUDT-IDS Rulebook Audience

This document has been prepared to inform staff within potential and current participants of the OA Book Usage Data Trust's International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) that create and share usage data about books (**Data Provider**) and/or receive usage data from other organizations (**Data Recipient**). Organizational units that house the following roles may find this document particularly useful: book usage data analysis and reporting, metadata and linked-data management, legal, cybersecurity and IT.

This document may also help the public, policy-makers, scholars, and other data spaces, to understand how the International Data Space model is being adapted to support data supply chains for innovation policy and scholarship impact.

Rulebook Format and Organization

This document is organized in six sections that address OAEBUDT governance, technologies, and administration.

- Section I (this section) provides an overview of the rulebook's purpose, audience, and organization.
- Section II defines roles, processes, terms and conditions related to OAEBUDT-IDS participation, including the roles and requirements of both usage data providers (**Data Provider**) and usage data recipients (**Data Recipient**)
- *Section III will summarize the standards and services supporting the OAEBUDT-IDS infrastructure (to be written post OAEBUDT-IDS technical pilot).*
- *Section IV will summarize the service level agreements in place with key OAEBUDT-IDS infrastructure providers (to be written post OAEBUDT-IDS technical pilot).*
- *Section V will describe and link to key legal agreements related to participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS (to be written 2024).*
- Section VI references additional resources and provides a glossary.

To facilitate trusted data exchange and use across participants in the OAEBUDT-IDS, Section II defines multiple facets for the OAEBUDT-IDS, including:

- book usage data quality and trust indicators that signal the state of usage data
- data sensitivity levels and acceptable use policies
- accountability measures and governance practices

About the OA eBook Usage Data Trust International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS)

The OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) aims to neutrally facilitate cross-platform usage data exchange, aggregation, and benchmarking through data-intermediation infrastructure for the scholarly communications industry. Through its International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS), it supports the controlled exchange of data between organizations that provide usage data to others (**Data Providers**), and organizations that receive, process, or innovate with usage data they receive from others, such as metrics and dashboard service providers (**Data Recipients**). As the administrative secretariat to the IDS trust network, the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** supports the IDS's function as a neutral data intermediary that meets the requirements of the European Data Governance Act and other national data regulations related to the exchange of sensitive data about the reading, access, and engagement tied to digital scholarship. More information about the OA Book Usage Data Trust effort can be found via its website (www.oabookusage.org).

SECTION II | DATA PROVIDER AND DATA RECIPIENT TERMS AND CONDITIONS

This section contains six parts.

Part I describes the roles and responsibilities of organizations that connect to the OAEBUDT-IDS. It describes the requirements organizations must meet to ensure trusted data exchange and use across all data space participants.. It explains the OAEBUDT-IDS role as a neutral data intermediary and the role of standards compliance for aggregated feeds of interoperable data.

Part II outlines required disclosures about the usage data feeds that participants must make when connecting to the OAEBUDT-IDS. The role of the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office in supporting accountability and self-certified disclosures is also explained.

Part III defines data sharing, use, and licensing terms and conditions for OAEBUDT-IDS participants. It notes different levels of sensitivity for different types of usage and impact data prior to outlining the requirements for OAEBUDT-IDS user authentication and OAEBUDT community limitations on the use of data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS. Finally, it outlines how participant reports of misrepresentations and non-compliance will be handled by the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office.

Part IV defines accountability measures used to maintain trust across the OAEBUDT-IDS, including cybersecurity, audit trails, and issue reporting. Liability, issue reporting and resolution processes are defined. Data retraction, correction, or modification is addressed. Actions the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office can take to maintain trust and accountability are defined.

Part V. defines OAEBUDT-IDS governance including the Coordinating Office, Board of Trustees, Board Committees. Advisory bodies and the fiscal, administrative, and legal sponsorship of the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office are clarified.

Part VI defines the administrative responsibilities of the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office such as enforcing the policies in this document and administering communications, membership and finances related to the OAEBUDT-IDS participation. Membership and Technical Service Provider contract administration is described. Finally, OAEBUDT-IDS onboarding and offboarding processes are described.

Part I. Roles in a Scalable International Data Space (IDS) to Interconnect Usage Data Providers and Recipients

As organizations increase data controls and limitations on data use in response to ethical concerns and regulatory compliance, there is a shared need to manage data exchange and processing through an automated semantic data governance layer that facilitates dynamic data exchange flows, processing, and controlled use across public and commercial parties. Organizations will still require data warehouses and data lakes to internally gather, index, and query diverse data within their own organizations and secure networks; however, a data space can provide an industry-wide hub through which secure environments can interoperate for specific, rule-based data brokerage.

To provide or access data securely across platforms and countries, organizations can connect to a data space as a **Data Provider** and/or **Data Recipient**. In the OAEBUDT-IDS, a creator of usage data participates as a **Data Provider**, providing usage data feed descriptions and connectivity to others through the IDS.

Book usage **Data Recipient** organizations can securely access such usage data feeds from multiple data providing platforms per data interoperability and reuse policies as described in this document and specified in contractual licensing, participation, data sharing and use agreements. A **Data Provider** may also act as a **Data Recipient**, drawing data from the OAEBUDT-IDS.

Usage Data Provider Definition

International Data Space Association (IDSA) Definition

The IDSA defines the **Data Provider** role for all interoperable, industry-agnostic data spaces. The IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM)⁹ describes how data is introduced into an IDS by the supplier of data which may be the data creator, data provider, and/or data owner depending on data licensing, management and authority. As the IDS-RAM describes:

*The Data Supplier is a role that induces data into the IDS ecosystem. Depending on the individual business and technical operation model, the business role Data Supplier typically assumes the basic roles Data Creator, Data Owner, and/or **Data Provider**.*

*The **Data Provider** makes data technically available in the IDS for transmission to a Data Customer on behalf of the Data Owner. To submit metadata to a Metadata Broker, or exchange data with a Data Consumer, the **Data Provider** uses software components that are compliant with the Reference Architecture Model of the International Data Spaces. Compliant software is available from Software Developers and App Developers.*

...

The Data Creator creates data, e.g. by generating data such as from a sensor or accessing data in backend IT systems... Usually, a participant acting as a Data Creator automatically assumes the role of the Data Owner. However, if rights or licenses on data are given to different participant, the same assumes the role of the Data Owner. In this case, Data Owner and Data Creator would be different participants.

*Initially, a participant acting as a Data Creator automatically assumes the role of the **Data Provider** as well. However, there may be cases in which the **Data Provider** is not the Data Creator, e.g. if the data is technically managed by a different entity than the Data Creator. ... In cases in which the Data Owner does not act as the **Data Provider** at the same time, the only activity of the Data Owner is to authorize a **Data Provider** to make its data available to be used by a Data Consumer. ([IDSA IDS-RAM 4.0](#), Last Accessed Nov 20, 2023)*

The IDSA's Rulebook for data spaces specifies that **Data Providers** must have legal authority over the data they make available in data spaces and as such, must be legal entities that can be held accountable. The definition reads,

Data Provider (essential): *The term data holder means a legal person, including public sector bodies and international organizations, or a natural person who is not a data subject with respect to the specific data in question, who has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data in accordance with applicable Union or national law. ([IDSA, 2023](#))¹⁰*

⁹ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0

¹⁰ Note: in this context, "legal person" is a legal term of art that refers to any entity, including individuals and organizations, capable of entering into a legal contract.

Book Usage Data Provider Specifications

To sustain trust and accountability, every stakeholder acting as a **Data Provider** in the OAEBUDT-IDS must retain control of, and responsibility for, the data they provide through the OAEBUDT-IDS. To participate, each **Data Provider** must: 1) be credible, 2) be trusted to exchange data, 3) be responsible for the data it makes available in the OAEBUDT-IDS, and 4) have the legal authority to distribute data to others.

1) To establish that it is a credible organization that can be held accountable for the data it provides through the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** must:

- a) be a recognized, legally incorporated organization in any country, including public institutions, corporations, and not-for-profit organizations, and
- b) provide a valid Tax Identification Number (TIN) or other documentation to establish their legal authority.

2) To establish that it is trusted to exchange data through the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** must:

- a) be a responsible member of the OAEBUDT in good membership standing (not inactive or on probation), and
- b) meet the requirements of **Data Providers** set forth in this Rulebook and associated OAEBUDT-IDS participation terms, conditions, and legal agreements.

Note: if an organization is actively preparing to exchange data as a “**Data Provider**” of the OAEBUDT-IDS but does not yet meet the above requirements of **Data Providers**, the organization may still formally affiliate with the OAEBUDT as a member, supporter, or research partner.

3) To establish that it maintains active responsibility for the usage data it makes available to others through the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** must:

- a) manage the platform, service, repository, or webpage that generated the usage data being provided through the OAEBUDT-IDS, and
- b) accept responsibility for the quality of all usage data they provide through the OAEBUDT-IDS; noting that quality is defined across multiple dimensions such as: accuracy, granularity, consistency, regularity, and
- c) investigate and respond to issues reported to the OAEBUDT-IDS related to the quality of the usage data exchanged by the **Data Provider**.

4) To establish that it holds and maintains the legal authority to distribute its usage data to others through the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** must:

- a) have the legal authority to make usage data available for processing or specific third party use through the OAEBUDT-IDS, and
- b) provide notification and obtain the necessary consent as is legally required prior to making usage data available for processing or specific third party use through the OAEBUDT-IDS.

5) To indicate how their data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS is allowed to be used, a Data Provider must indicate which allowable uses are permitted for their Data Connectors, choosing among provided options including:

- i) scholarly use, i.e. for research or teaching
- ii) non-profit use, i.e. providing a good or service for free
- iii) commercial use, i.e. for providing a good or service for payment regardless of for-profit or not-for-profit organizational status
- iv) internal research and analysis to support decision-making, i.e. demographic analysis

- v) public policy research
- vi) advocacy
- vii) artificial intelligence applications or training
- viii) other use

Usage Data Recipient Definition

Note: Within the OAEBUDT-IDS, the exchange of usage data is not expected to be monetized, therefore the term **Data Recipient** is purposefully used instead of the IDSA term “Data Consumer”.

International Data Space Association Definition

The IDSA defines the **Data Recipient** role across all interoperable, industry-agnostic data spaces, including industries where such data is monetized through marketplaces resulting in data recipients being referred to as data consumers. Accordingly, within the Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM), the IDSA describes the relationships between those who receive data, namely data consumers and data users:

*The Data Consumer receives data from a **Data Provider**. From a business process modeling perspective, the Data Consumer is the mirror entity of the **Data Provider**; the activities performed by the Data Consumer are therefore similar to the activities performed by the **Data Provider**...*

Similar to the Data Owner being the legal entity that has the legal control over its data, the Data User is the legal entity that has the legal right to use the data of a Data Owner as specified by the usage policy.

The Data User can be identical with the Data Consumer. However, there may be scenarios in which these roles are assumed by different participants. For example, a patient could use a web-based software system to manage their personal health data and grant access to this data to a health coach. The data could be received from a hospital. In this case, the health coach would be the Data User and the provider of the web-based software system would be the Data Consumer.

*In existing, mostly quite static relations, the Data Customer and Data Supplier already know each other and intend to exchange specific data sets.... In these cases, the Data Consumer directly requests data (and the corresponding metadata) from the **Data Provider** or the **Data Provider** pushes data directly to the Data Consumer....*

*Like a **Data Provider**, the Data Consumer may log the details of a successful (or unsuccessful) data exchange transaction at a Clearing House, use Apps to enrich, transform, etc. the data received, or use a Metadata Broker to retrieve data sources. ([IDSA IDS-RAM 4.0](#), Last Accessed Nov 20, 2023)*

The IDSA's Rulebook for data spaces specifies that **Data Recipients** must have the legal right to use the data they receive.

Data consumer (essential): The term data user means a natural or legal person who has lawful access to certain personal or non-personal data and has the right, including under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in the case of personal data, to use that data for commercial or non-commercial purposes. ([IDSA Rulebook](#), Last Accessed Nov 20, 2023)

Book Usage Data Recipient Specifications

To maintain trust within the OAEBUDT-IDS network, each book usage data stakeholder acting as a **Data Recipient** agrees to use data accessed through the OAEBUDT-IDS in accordance with the terms and licensing supplied by their **Data Provider(s)**. Recipients of data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS must: 1) be accountable, 2) be trusted, and 3) be responsible for the data they receive.

1) To establish that it can be held accountable for the data they access via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Recipient** must:

- a) be a recognized, legally incorporated organization in any country, including public institutions, corporations, and not-for-profit organizations, and
- b) provide a valid Tax Identification Number (TIN) or other documentation to establish their legal identity.

2) To establish that it is trusted to receive data via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Recipient** must:

- a) be a responsible member of the OA Book Usage Data Trust in good membership standing, i.e. adhering to all terms and conditions and not inactive or on probation, and
- b) meet the requirements of **Data Recipients** set forth in this Rulebook and associated OAEBUDT-IDS participation terms, conditions, and legal agreements.

3) To establish that it maintains active responsibility for the usage data it accesses via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Recipient** must:

- b) accept responsibility to only use the data accessed through the OAEBUDT-IDS in a pre-agreed way,
- c) indicate how data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS will be used, choosing among provided options including:
 - i) scholarly use, i.e. for research or teaching
 - ii) non-profit use, i.e. providing a good or service for free
 - iii) commercial use, i.e. for providing a good or service for payment regardless of for-profit or not-for-profit organizational status
 - iv) internal research and analysis to support decision-making, i.e. demographic analysis
 - v) public policy research
 - vi) advocacy
 - vii) artificial intelligence applications or training
 - viii) other use
- d) For each use selected, **Data Recipient** must describe for **Data Provider** the specific intended uses in free text to provide sufficient transparency to the **Data Provider**, and
- c) report to the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** any issues related to the quality of the usage data received from a **Data Provider**

As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT-IDS will not discriminate among **Data Recipient(s)** when providing access to information as long as **Data Recipient** remains in good standing and compliant with the rules and policies set forth in this Rulebook and related agreements and terms pertaining to Data Trust participation and the sharing and use of OA Book Usage data obtained through the Data Trust.

OAEBUDT-IDS Participation as a Data Provider and Data Recipient

An organization can interact with the OAEBUDT-IDS as a usage **Data Provider** that makes data available to others and as a usage **Data Recipient** that receives usage data from other platforms and services. An entity may act as **Data Recipient** in the OAEBUDT-IDS even if they are not a **Data Provider**.

The onboarding process and associated cost-recovery mechanisms tied to OAEBUDT-IDS participation may differ for **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients**. The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** aims to streamline processes for all organizations. Additional information will be gathered during the OAEBUDT-IDS pilots and incorporated herein.

Neutral Multi-party Usage Data Exchange via the OAEBUDT-IDS

Recognizing that usage data is created by diverse **Data Providers** that may have high or low capacities for usage data normalization, standardization, and management; the OAEBUDT-IDS will transit usage data regardless of its quality or compliance with a specific standard. The OAEBUDT-IDS will make available and support the exchange of all usage that **Data Providers** make available through the OAEBUDT-IDS regardless of indicated data quality trust levels or standards compliance.

As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT-IDS must transit all such usage data between **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients**, provided the parties abide by the rules and terms of the OAEBUDT and remain Active Members in good standing with the OAEBUDT. Data connections may be temporarily impacted by investigations and issue resolution processes as described in the [Accountability Mechanisms](#) section of this rulebook.

For such general data exchange in the OAEBUDT-IDS, data quality is assured by the **Data Provider** and made available to **Data Recipients** on an “as-is” basis. Each **Data Provider** must provide metadata about their usage data, including details on data provenance and pre-processing as is described in [Part IV](#) of this rulebook. **Data Recipients** accept responsibility for the data they receive, recognizing that trust indicators and metadata was self-certified by each **Data Provider**.

To support diverse, inclusive participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS from a variety of **Data Providers**, self-certified data quality trust indicators provided by **Data Providers** will be transparently communicated to **Data Recipients** through the OAEBUDT-IDS. **Data Recipients** must take care to manage variance across data quality indicators when processing, analyzing, or otherwise using data received through the OAEBUDT-IDS.

In the OAEBUDT-IDS, **Data Providers** may make available book level and/or chapter level usage data. **Data Providers** are not required to have the same level of data quality indicators or data exchange levels for all data made available via the OAEBUDT-IDS. This allows the OAEBUDT to be inclusive of **Data Providers** who are adopting standards and maturing internal processes.

Evidence of Standards-Compliance to Support Data Aggregation and Processing

Interoperability is required for **Data Recipients** to trust the aggregation and benchmarking of data created across different platforms and services. As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT-IDS will communicate to **Data Recipients** which data connectors are identified by **Data Providers** as standards conformant or compliant (see ["Item-Level" Data Accuracy](#)).

Should the OAEBUDT-IDS generate and make available via an IDS App Store values calculated from multiple **Data Providers** (e.g. added together for aggregated totals or averaged into a composite benchmark value for a specific sub-grouping of **Data Providers**), evidence of standards-compliance will be required for **Data Provider** usage data to be included.

Part II. Disclosures to Foster Book Usage Data Quality and Trust

How OAEBUDT-IDS Data Providers and Data Recipients Influence Data Quality and Credibility

Multiple elements assist **Data Recipients** with understanding the nature, quality, interoperability and credibility of data made available by **Data Providers**. To support trusted data exchange, all participants in the OAEBUDT trust network agree to make transparent the data provenance, stewardship, and licensing for the usage data sent or received via the OAEBUDT-IDS as described in this document and its related agreements.

Table: Term Definitions

Data Provenance	Details about the origin, transmission, and storage of usage data. ¹¹
Data Processing and Stewardship	Details related to the usage data management under the Data Provider , such as standards adherence, data processing, security and access, and relevant metadata.
Licensing	Details related to the application and sharing of usage data

Data Providers accept full responsibility for accurately describing the usage data they provide via the OAEBUDT-IDS. Within the OAEBUDT-IDS interface, a **Data Provider** will be prompted to input the following information when they are configuring their **Data Connector**. This section describes the “metadata about usage data” that will be required to establish a **Data Provider’s Data Connector** with the OAEBUDT-IDS.

Data Recipients accept full responsibility for accurately crediting and passing on **Data Provider’s** information (where applicable) and describing the **Data Recipient’s** own application and use of the usage data they receive.

1. Usage Data Provenance Disclosure

To be transparent about the usage data it makes available to others, a **Data Provider** must describe the lineage of organizations that created the usage data by listing each organization involved in the creation and processing of the usage data prior to it being made available through the OAEBUDT-IDS. At a minimum this includes providing the following information for each organization involved in the provenance chain up to and including the **Data Provider**:

- a) Legal Organization Name
- b) Country of Organization
- c) Website of Organization
- d) Contact Person at Organization
- e) Email Address for Contact Person

2. Usage Data Processing and Stewardship Disclosure

To be transparent about the usage data it makes available to others, a **Data Provider** must provide a text-based description of all transformations or processing conducted on the usage data prior to making it

¹¹ See US National Institute of Standards and Technologies Definition: https://csrc.nist.gov/glossary/term/data_provenance

available through the OAEBUDT-IDS (noting algorithms, code, or standards that were applied where applicable, and whether such algorithms, code or standards are proprietary or available for open review).

3. Quality Assurance Measures Disclosure

For each data feed connected to the OAEBUDT-IDS, a Data Provider must provide a text-based description of measures taken to ensure accuracy, completeness, and reliability of usage data, such as validation processes, error detection, and correction mechanisms.

4. Data Licensing, Sharing, and Use Terms Disclosure

For each data feed connected to the OAEBUDT-IDS (i.e. **Data Connector**), **Data Providers** must provide a description of the data's licensing, sharing and use terms. **Data Providers'** responses will be published and made openly available to OAEBUDT-IDS participants to transparently describe the state of the usage data feed.

5. Other Usage Data Related Information Disclosure

To be transparent about the usage data it makes available to others, a **Data Provider** must provide information about the stewardship and licensing of the usage data it provides through the OAEBUDT-IDS. In particular, a **Data Provider** must communicate the data quality trust level indicators described below.

Communicating Data Quality Through Transparent Trust Level Indicators

For each OAEBUDT-IDS **Data Connector**, **Data Providers** must self-assess and accurately certify a description of their data across the following six data quality trust indicators. **Data Providers** will select among three provided descriptions for each indicator. **Data Providers'** responses will be openly shared with OAEBUDT-IDS participants to transparently describe the state of the usage data feed.

1. Usage Data "Item-Level" Data Accuracy

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in a usage data feed's compliance with a given community standard, such as COUNTER. Standards conformance and independent certification of standards compliance increase the level of trust from least to most trusted.

Options made available for **Data Provider** selection include:

- | | |
|---------|--|
| Level 1 | Not conformant to any published, community standard; e.g. Non-COUNTER Compliant |
| Level 2 | Conformant or self-certified as compliant to an industry standard; e.g. COUNTER conformance for past or current version of the COUNTER Code of Practice |
| Level 3 | Third-party certified compliance with a published community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance for the Current Code of Practice, as evidenced by listing in https://registry.projectcounter.org/ |

2. Usage Data "Item-level" Data Generation Transparency

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in how a usage data feed was generated. Less transparent data processing methods or descriptions generate lower levels of trust. Options for **Data Provider** selection include:

- | | |
|---------|--|
| Level 1 | Ad hoc, standard, or common proprietary usage data processing software with no description of data generation method |
| Level 2 | Standard or common proprietary usage data processing software and basic description on the data generation method |

Level 3 Open source usage data processing software & full description on the data generation method

3. Usage Data "Item-level" Data Delivery Reliability

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in how reliable the delivery and access is for a given usage Data Connector. Not to be confused with how often data is made available (see 4. Data Frequency below), this reliability indicator highlights any variance in the delivery of usage data. Irregular data publishing or delivery reduces the level of trust. Options for **Data Provider** selection include:

- Level 1 Irregular availability or variance in the reporting periods over time
- Level 2 Data delivered with some exceptions
- Level 3 Data delivered on time without exceptions

4. Usage Data "Item-level" Data Frequency

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in how frequently data within a given usage data feed is updated. Not to be confused with one's confidence that the data will be published (see 3. Data Delivery Reliability above), the data frequency indicator highlights how current a usage data feed is. Irregular data publishing or delivery reduces the level of trust. Options for **Data Provider** selection include:

- Level 1 Irregular data delivery frequency
- Level 2 Regular metric publication on at least a monthly frequency
- Level 3 On-demand metric exchange

5. Usage Data "Item-level" Data Granularity

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in how granular the data is. Unmerged data, transparent data sources, and raw web analytics data generate higher levels of trust. It is important to note that with increased granularity comes increased data sensitivity and related security and privacy requirements for both **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** (See [Data Sensitivity](#).) Options for **Data Provider** selection include:

- Level 1 When all usage data is merged into one single number without the ability to check the different elements of the data or how the data was calculated
- Level 2 Deliver usage data without merging it and providing data generation transparency
- Level 3 Data sources are fully available and include GDPR compliant raw web analytics

6. Usage Data "Item-level" Data Consistency

This indicator reflects the level of trust a **Data Recipient** can place in how consistent the data is within a Data Connector. Changes in data generation methods over time reduce trust as does a lack of transparency when a change of data generation method occurs unprompted by standards compliance. Options for **Data Provider** selection include:

- Level 1 Multiple generation methods used over the past year for the same type of data and/or the change of method is not declared
- Level 2 No more than two generation methods used to generate the same type of data over the past two years and the change of method is declared

Level 3 Consistent generation method used for data for more than two years and the change of method is due to complying with a published, community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance

Table: Data Quality Trust Indicator Levels from Least to Most Trusted

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
OAEBU "Item-Level" Data Accuracy	<u>Not conformant</u> to any published, community standard; e.g. Non-COUNTER Compliant	<u>Conformant or self-certified as compliant</u> to an industry standard; e.g. COUNTER conformance for past or current version of the COUNTER Code of Practice	<u>Third-party certified compliance</u> with a published community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance for the Current Code of Practice, as evidenced by listing in https://registry.projectcounter.org/
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Generation Transparency	<u>Ad hoc, standard, or common proprietary</u> usage data processing software with <u>no description</u> of data generation method	<u>Standard or common proprietary</u> usage data processing software and <u>basic description</u> on the data generation method	<u>Open source</u> usage data processing software and <u>full description</u> on the data generation method
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Delivery Reliability	<u>Irregular</u> availability or variance in the reporting periods over time	Data delivered with <u>some exceptions</u>	Data delivered <u>on time without exceptions</u>
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Frequency	<u>Irregular</u> data delivery frequency	Regular metric publication on <u>at least a monthly frequency</u>	<u>On-demand</u> metric exchange
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Granularity	All usage data is <u>merged</u> into one single number with <u>zero ability to check</u> the different data elements or how the data was calculated	Deliver usage data <u>without merging it</u> and <u>providing data generation transparency</u>	Data <u>sources are fully available</u> and <u>include GDPR compliant raw web analytics</u>
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Consistency	<u>Multiple</u> generation methods used over the past year for the same type of data and/or the change of method <u>is not declared</u>	<u>No more than 2</u> generation methods used to generate the same type of data over the past two years and the <u>change of method is declared</u>	Consistent generation method used for data for <u>more than two years</u> and the change of method is due to complying with a published, community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance

OAEBUDT Coordinating Office Role in Verifying Data Quality Trust Indicators

To minimize operational and legal overhead costs, **Data Provider** self-certifications will not be actively verified or monitored by the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**. Instead, to support trust, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will hold **Data Providers** accountable to their self-certifications through a variety of mechanisms, including OAEBUDT membership status, Data Connector operational status, and community reporting and issue investigation mechanisms. (See [Accountability Mechanisms Section](#))

Self-certification by Data Providers of Third Party Validation of Standards Compliance

To support the trusted interoperability of data submitted through the OAEBUDT-IDS, a high level of standardization is necessary as evidenced by compliance with an industry standard. For a **Data Provider's** Data Connector to be eligible for inclusion in a standards-specific API offered via the OAEBUDT-IDS, the **Data Provider** must provide evidence of being certified as compliant with said established community standard by a third party authority. Examples for standard-specific APIs are noted below.

Certified COUNTER Compliance for COUNTER-specific aggregate or benchmarking APIs

To have their data included in COUNTER-specific APIs made available via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** must certify that their data is compliant with the current COUNTER Code of Practice, or the immediate past version of the Code of Practice if a new version was released in the past 24 months. To be included in COUNTER-related APIs that require the processing of data across platforms, **Data Providers** must self-certify that they are listed on the COUNTER Compliant Platform Registry - <https://registry.projectcounter.org>.

Potential OAEBUDT-IDS Aggregated Book (Title-level) Usage APIs

To be included within the following technical pilot OAEBUDT-IDS APIs, **Data Providers** must 1) provide proof of independent certification of standards compliance and 2) provide an ISBN and DOI for individual book instances.

- COUNTER Compliant Multi-Platform Item-level Usage Aggregation - Multi-Platform Book Level Views API
- COUNTER Compliant Multi-Platform Item-level Usage Aggregation - Multi-Platform Book Level Downloads API

Potential OAEBUDT-IDS Aggregated Chapter Usage APIs

To be included within the following technical pilot OAEBUDT-IDS APIs, **Data Providers** must 1) provide proof of independent certification of standards compliance and 2) provide DOIs for all chapters.

- COUNTER-Compliant Multi-Platform Item-level Usage Aggregation - Multi-Platform Chapter Views
- COUNTER Compliant Multi-Platform Item-level Usage Aggregation - Multi-Platform Chapter Downloads

Licensing of Data From Processing APIs (i.e. Aggregate or Benchmarking)

If allowable per ongoing research into the regulated functions of data intermediaries in the context of laws such as the European Data Governance Act, Digital Marketplaces Act, and Data Act; the OAEBUDT may offer the aggregation or averaging of usage data across Data Connectors. Data Providers would opt-in to such additional processing by enabling such within the OAEBUDT-IDS App Store. Such new composite values will be made available to Data Recipients to relicense on a non-exclusive basis.

Support for Additional Standards Compliance

Recognizing that standards evolve and emerge, the OAEBUDT-IDS as a neutral intermediary will support multiple industry standards, as specified in the [Standards supporting the OAEBUDT-IDS Network Infrastructure](#) section of this document.

Part III. Usage Data Sharing and Use Policies

The ability to specify, control, and limit the application and processing of data that transits the OAEBUDT-IDS is a key function of the IDS trust ecosystem. An IDSA position paper on data usage controls explains how downstream **Data Recipient's** usage of data can be governed through an IDS.

*Usage control is an extension to traditional access control...It is about the specification and enforcement of restrictions regulating what must (not) happen to data. Thus, usage control is concerned with requirements that pertain to data processing (obligations), rather than data access (provisions). Usage control is relevant in the context of intellectual property protection, compliance with regulations, and digital rights management.¹²...In contrast to access control, where access to specific resources (e.g., a service or a file) is restricted, **the IDS architecture additionally supports data-centric usage control.** In general, the overall goal is to enforce usage restrictions for data after access has been granted. **Therefore, the purpose of usage control is to bind policies to data being exchanged and to continuously control the way how messages may be processed, aggregated, or forwarded to other endpoints.** This data-centric perspective allows the user to continuously control data flows, rather than accesses to services.¹³ - **Emphasis added***

To support trusted data exchange across all participants in the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** and [technical IDS service providers](#) that operate core services of the infrastructure will work to prevent a number of potential issues that could compromise the authenticity and security of data being exchanged. Issues could arise from intentional, bad actions such as the unlicensed scraping or harvesting of data, or the unauthorized publication of data. Unintended events could impact trust and result in a loss of control over exchanged data, for example through cyberattacks or compelled legal disclosures. Misinterpretations of data quality and fit-to-purpose, especially if AI and ML training is involved, could result in complex issues and reduced trust.

To neutrally support diverse use cases for usage data across the scholarly publishing ecosystem of **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients**, the OAEBUDT-IDS will allow both parties to send and receive semantic, machine readable data use and reuse policy elements. This will be supported by:

- 1) **Data Provider** interfaces to designate allowable licensed uses of particular Data Connectors and view associated OAEBUDT-IDS logs relating to their own use of the OAEBUDT-IDS as well as associated **Data Recipients** use of the **Data Provider's** own Data Connectors
- 2) **Data Recipient** interfaces to find, assess, and interoperate with Data Connectors and view logs associated with their own activity within the OAEBUDT-IDS
- 3) Accountability mechanisms managed by the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** to address issues that arise.

¹² Eitel, A., Jung, C., Brandstädter, R., Hosseinzadeh, A., Bader, S., Kühnle, C., Birnstill, P., Brost, G., Gall, Bruckner, F., Weißenberg, N., & Korth, B. (2021). Usage Control in the International Data Spaces (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5268926> pg 11

¹³ Eitel, A., Jung, C., Brandstädter, R., Hosseinzadeh, A., Bader, S., Kühnle, C., Birnstill, P., Brost, G., Gall, Bruckner, F., Weißenberg, N., & Korth, B. (2021). Usage Control in the International Data Spaces (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5268926> , pg 13.

Data Provider Specific Usage Data Sharing and Use Licenses

As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT-IDS facilitates the exchange of usage data between **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** in line with existing legal data sharing and usage agreements and licenses executed directly between the parties outside of the OAEBUDT. Recognizing that ethical and appropriate use may be defined differently across the world, **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** must organizationally abide by both the terms that accompany data made available via the OAEBUDT and the legal restrictions or requirements of the local jurisdiction's involved.

Within the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Provider** can only make available data that they have legal authority over. If a **Data Provider** has no legal authority to share the data, the **Data Provider** cannot make the data available or apply data licensing, use, or reuse terms via the OAEBUDT-IDS.

A **Data Provider** can only apply usage requirements, limitations, or licenses to data they make available via the OAEBUDT-IDS if:

- a) the **Data Provider** created the data and has full legal authority over such data, or
- b) the **Data Provider** certifies that they have been granted the rights to share the data under such terms by the legal entity¹⁴ with authority over that data, (for example, through an existing vendor contract or Open License).

Recognizing that there are [multiple levels of data sensitivity](#) associated with the format and type of usage data exchanged through the OAEBUDT-IDS, **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** have the ability to specify specific licensed uses for specific **Data Connectors** in line with agreements between the parties made outside of the OAEBUDT. As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT cannot force a **Data Provider** to opt-in to any specific license or use of their usage data via the OAEBUDT-IDS. To support ethical and trusted applications of data, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will enforce a limited set of use restrictions established by the [OAEBUDT Community Governance](#) and [described below](#). **Data Providers** should carefully consider the use of Non-Derivative license types, as such could restrict data aggregation, benchmarking, or privacy protection oriented processing.

To receive data from a specific **Data Provider** via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a **Data Recipient** must:

- a) be a member of the OAEBUDT-IDS community in good standing
- b) have an existing legally binding agreement, license, or permission that authorizes access to the **Data Provider's** usage data through the OAEBUDT-IDS
- c) Accept full responsibility and legal liability to manage, share, and use the **Data Provider's** usage data according to such terms

Varied Sensitivity of Book Usage and Impact Data Types

To best support Open Science, the OAEBUDT community aims to support scholarship usage data exchange that is transparent and as open as legally possible. However, the usage and impact related data elements that could transverse the OAEBUDT-IDS vary greatly. Granular usage data, i.e. web analytics relating use to unique individual identifiers or IP addresses, can improve decision making and are in demand for a host of use cases; however, the access and use of such sensitive information raises a host of privacy, ethics, security, and regulatory compliance issues that must be carefully managed by both **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients**. Like other global IDS systems, the OAEBUDT-IDS exists to help organizations reduce such risks and related data stewardship costs through controlled, secure data exchange.

¹⁴ The IDSA refers to this role as the "Data Owner"

Data Providers may require **Data Recipients** to continue to manage usage data received through the OAEBUDT-IDS in line with specific requirements to reduce legal, ethical, or personal risks. While **Data Providers** accept full responsibility for the data they connect to the OAEBUDT-IDS, **Data Recipients** accept full responsibility for their downstream sharing and use of such information .

The OAEBUDT-IDS encourages the exchange of data in a way that is as open as legally possible, but as controlled as necessary to address legal, ethical, and personal risks. The following tables describe less sensitive and highly sensitive usage data types for **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** to consider as they establish bilateral usage data sharing and use terms.

Table: Less Sensitive Usage and Impact Data Elements

Usage and Impact Data Elements Recommendation to offer via OAEBUDT-IDS as open as legally possible
OA Book Metadata Elements
Item-level open bibliographic metadata
Item-level ONIX* records *initial metadata feed for OAEBUDT technical pilot; others may be added over time based on the needs of the community
Global Usage Data Elements
Usage event data associated with specific countries or regions
Usage event data associated with specific market segments, disciplines, or domains
Organization-Specific Usage Data Elements
Usage event data for specific publishers
Usage event data for specific institutions (e.g. universities, libraries, platforms)
Book Citation Data Elements
News or social media citation of an item-level work
Educational - syllabi or publication citation of an item-level work
Research - patent or publication citation of an item-level work
Public citation of an item-level work (e.g. Crossref Events Data)
Usage Benchmarking Data Elements
Benchmarked average usage value calculated for items in standard categories (e.g. BISAC subject codes)

Table: Highly Sensitive Usage and Impact Data Elements

Usage and Impact Data Elements Recommendation to offer via OAEBUDT-IDS with most control due to high legal, ethical, or personal risk
Individual-Specific OA Book Usage Data Elements
Individual usage events at an individual IP address level of detail
Individual usage events at an individual person level of detail (i.e. unique identifier - i.e. ORCID, screen name, etc.)
Unprocessed web page log files for unique items as defined per COUNTER COP 5.1.6.1 as: “text files representing individual HTTP requests, including the user host name or IP address, the date and time of the

request, the requested file name, the HTTP response status and size, the referring URL and the browser information.”
OA Book Reader Engagement - Behavioral Data Elements
Page annotation activity
Duration and/or timestamps related to viewing activity

Affiliated, Authenticated Individual Access to OAEBUDT-IDS

User Identity Authentication

Unique verifiable identifiers for identity and authentication management (IAM) will be required for each **Data Provider** and **Data Recipient** user accessing the OAEBUDT-IDS. This requirement allows the OAEBUDT-IDS to foster trust among data space participants by holding participants accountable for the actions they take with the data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS.

While there is public value in unaffiliated individual access to usage data, especially when such data is made available via public domain without use limitations, it is challenging to manage and maintain trust, accountability, liability and privacy in a network when providing data access to unaffiliated individuals. Managing unaffiliated individual access would increase privacy, ethical, and compliance risks and related staffing and legal costs. The OAEBUDT will focus first on providing data access to organization-affiliated individuals, recognizing that unrestricted usage data in the public domain is likely also accessible outside of the OAEBUDT-IDS.

OAEBUDT Community Limitations on the Use of Data Accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS

While the OAEBUDT-IDS acts as a neutral data intermediary that supports the exchange and use of data according to terms and conditions set by parties outside of the IDS, the network of OAEBUDT-IDS participants must adhere to shared principles to ensure trust. All participants in the OAEBUDT, including **Data Providers, Data Recipients, Core IDS Service Providers, Coordinating Office** and **Governance Bodies**, must abide by the following restrictions.

Given the severity of the issues below, if an OAEBUDT-IDS participant is suspected or reported for any of these activities, during the issue investigation period, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will:

- put their membership into a probationary status
- suspend all active Data Connectors.

Prohibited Uses of Data Accessed via the OAEBUDT

To maintain trust across the OAEBUDT-IDS network of participants, the following uses of data accessed via the Data Trust are expressly prohibited. Reporting mechanisms will allow any OAEBUDT-IDS participant to identify potential breaches of trust for further investigation (See [Participant Accountability Mechanisms](#)) Reports of non-compliance will be investigated by the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**. Data trust membership and participation will be subject to the results of the investigation as defined below. If an OAEBUDT participant is found to have engaged in any of these activities, actions will be taken to remedy the situation. These actions may include: OAEBUDT membership wide communications, probation, suspension, or legal liability, as discussed below.

Prohibited uses of data accessed via the OAEBUDT include:

1. Scraping, harvesting, or otherwise bulk downloading data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS unless expressly allowed by a specific **Data Provider's** terms and conditions
2. Forwarding or passing along OAEBUDT data outside of the OAEBUDT-IDS environment
3. Identifying or re-identifying unique individuals from masked or otherwise anonymized information accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS

Prohibition on Misrepresentation by OAEBUDT Participants

As a trust network, the OAEBUDT-IDS aims to foster the exchange of trusted data among trusted parties. Misrepresentations by OAEBUDT-IDS participants, either about themselves or their data, directly impact trust across the OAEBUDT-IDS network. To reinforce trust, the following misrepresentations are expressly prohibited. Reports of non-compliance will be investigated by the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**. Data trust membership and participation will be subject to the results of the investigation as defined below. If an OAEBUDT participant is found to have engaged in any of these activities, actions will be taken to remedy the situation. These actions may include: OAEBUDT membership-wide communications, probation, suspension, or legal liability, as discussed below.

1. Misrepresentation of one's identity or organizational affiliation when interacting with the OAEBUDT-IDS
2. Misrepresentation by a **Data Recipient** of their intended use of the data
3. Falsification, inflation, omission, or other intentional misrepresentation of data exchanged by a **Data Provider** or accessed by a **Data Recipient**

Table: Example OAEBUDT-IDS Trust Issues by Severity, Urgency and Suggested Resolution Timeframe

Trust Issue	Severity	Urgency	Targeted Resolution Timeframe
Misrepresentation of data quality trust indicators	Moderate to High	Moderate to High	Within 10 business days
Manipulation of data	Moderate to High	Moderate to High	Within 10 business days
Data Connector security protocol breach or failure, including cyberattacks	High	High	Within 2 business days
Harm experienced by OAEBUDT participant (e.g. legal, reputational or financial)	High	High	Within 2 business days
Unlicensed use of OAEBUDT-IDS accessed data	High	High	Within 2 business days
Bulk scraping or harvesting to rehost data outside of OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem	High	High	Within 2 business days
Harm to Individual privacy, e.g. via individual reader identification or reidentification	High	High	Within 2 business days

Part IV. Accountability Mechanisms

The provision of accurate [disclosures](#) and data by **Data Providers** is necessary to foster trust across OAEBUDT-IDS participants. Similarly, each **Data Recipient's** management, stewardship, and use of data accessed via the OAEBUDT is critical to maintaining trust and assuring that received data is used in accordance with the terms and conditions of **Data Providers**.

If organizational OAEBUDT-IDS participants are not held accountable to the [terms](#) that accompany OAEBUDT-IDS participation, accidental and/or unintended consequences could result in real harm to individuals or organizations. Therefore, each OAEBUDT-IDS participant organization is responsible for the actions taken by the users who access the system through their OAEBUDT member affiliated OAEBUDT-IDS credentials.

The OAEBUDT network of participants works to technically reduce the risk of such incidents occurring through security, identity and authentication mechanisms coupled with logged data exchange transactions via the OAEBUDT-IDS. These technical measures support contractual obligations established through OAEBUDT-IDS Membership and OAEBUDT-IDS participation. Recognizing that **Data Providers, Data Recipients,** and **OAEBUDT-IDS Technical Service Providers** manage the liability and risk associated with their use of the OAEBUDT-IDS, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** manages a number of accountability mechanisms to support adherence to and reporting of non-compliance related to OAEBUDT-IDS participation.

The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** supports OAEBUDT-IDS Participant reporting of potential issues for investigation and resolution. This section describes such accountability mechanisms and describes an issue reporting, investigation, and resolution process for OAEBUDT-IDS participants. Recognizing that some data quality and trust issues stem from unintentional actions or events, the issue resolution process explains issue resolution timelines and steps the OAEBUDT-IDS may implement to protect the data space's integrity during an active investigation.

Certified Levels of OAEBUDT-IDS Participant Security

To ensure trust, the OAEBUDT-IDS will implement the IDS Certification Scheme¹⁵, which allows participants to provide assurance to other OAEBUDT-IDS participants by certifying security measures at one of three levels. **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** will have the option to certify at three levels, ranging from a basic, low-cost entry-level self-assessment option to independently evaluated certifications of internal management systems and control frameworks. To ensure continuity and security at the heart of the OAEBUDT-IDS, organizations fulfilling the OAEBUDT-IDS **Clearinghouse** or **Identity Provider** roles will be required to certify at the highest security level to comply with IDS standards.¹⁶ Organizations providing the OAEBUDT-IDS with services as a **Metadata Broker, App Store Provider, Vocabulary Provider,** or other service will be required to undergo "Member level" security certification as established by the IDSA. The rationale for the differing security levels for core IDS services is provided in an IDSA whitepaper as follows:

¹⁵ Menz, N., Otto, P. D. B., & Resetko, A. (2019). Framework for the IDS Certification Scheme 2.0 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5657989>

¹⁶ Menz, N., Otto, P. D. B., & Resetko, A. (2019). Framework for the IDS Certification Scheme 2.0 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5657989>, pg 11.

Broker Service Providers, providers of Clearing House services, the App Store Provider, and the Vocabulary Provider deal only with metadata, transactions, or apps (k.i.e. They do not work with the sensitive payload data which the Industrial Data Space is designed to protect). The risk associated with possible breaches of confidentiality, integrity, and availability of metadata is lower... Nevertheless, an attacker succeeding in exfiltrating or corrupting metadata, or impeding the availability of metadata, would be able to cause considerable damage to the Industrial Data Space or targeted participants – especially if such successful attacks would remain undetected over extended periods of time. Therefore, evaluation and certification tailored to the specific risk profiles of and security mechanisms employed by broker service providers, providers of clearing house services, app store providers, and vocabulary providers is proposed in order to ensure a sufficient degree of security against the risks mentioned. ([Framework for the IDS Certification Scheme 2.0](#) , Last Accessed Jan 30, 2024)

{Further refinement of this section is expected during the technical pilots}

Audit Trail of Data Connector Access and Transmission

The OAEBUDT-IDS will generate logs to make data access transparent. The OAEBUDT-IDS audit log will record activities taken by **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** within the OAEBUDT-IDS environment. **Data Providers** will have access to audit logs for the data they make available via the OAEBUDT-IDS via Data Connectors. **Data Recipients** will have access to the audit logs for their own activity. The **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** staff and governance will have access to all audit logs, as will OAEBUDT-IDS legal and technical service providers on an as needed basis.

Issue Reporting to the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office

OAEBUDT-IDS participants will have access to a standard mechanism to report the following issues to the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** for issue investigation, mitigation, and resolution. *Note: specific procedures for issue investigation, risk mitigation, participation notification, and issue remediation will be modeled during technical pilots and detailed in this section.*

Legal Responsibilities of Organizations within the OAEBUDT

It is the responsibility of the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**, under the guidance of the OAEBUDT Board of Trustees, fiscal sponsor, and legal representative, to manage contracts, membership and compliance for the OAEBUDT-IDS. The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office, Board of Trustees**, fiscal sponsor and legal representative are not liable or responsible for the actions of any **Data Provider, Data Recipient, or OAEBUDT-IDS Service Provider**; these organizations are directly responsible for their own individual actions and data within the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem. The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** is responsible for holding all OAEBUDT-IDS participants accountable to their terms and conditions of participation.

Data Inconsistency Issue Reporting

OAEBUDT-IDS participants will be able to report suspicious or incorrect data provided by **Data Providers** through the OAEBUDT-IDS, including suspicious usage data inconsistency.

Data Quality Indicator Misrepresentation Issue Reporting

OAEBUDT-IDS participants will be able to report suspicious or incorrect [data quality trust level indicators](#) provided by **Data Providers**.

Contractual Non Compliance Issue Reporting

OAEBUDT-IDS participants will be able to report suspected agreement noncompliance for any OAEBUDT Participant or OAEBUDT-IDS service provider.

Issue Reporting Process

When submitting an issue report, OAEBUDT-IDS Participants must identify themselves and provide a contact for further communications. The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will use this information for communications during the issue resolution process.

The method for an OAEBUDT-IDS Participant to report an issue is... {To be determined in Technical Pilot; anticipate a reporting form that will feed information either into a ticket-tracking system (ideal), or email and spreadsheet for staff follow-up; will describe process and add link to form once it is available}

Issue Notification and Investigation Process

The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will notify the **Data Provider(s)** and/or **Data Recipient(s)** impacted and/or named within the received incident report and will provide full access to the submitted issue report.

Depending on the severity and urgency of the issue, the **Data Provider** or **Data Recipient** subject of the issue investigation will have a set number of business days from the date of notification receipt to:

- acknowledge receipt of the notice (1 business day)
- conduct their internal investigation (varies depending on issue)
- develop and propose their issue resolution action plan as a response back to the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** and reporting OAEBUDT-IDS participant. (varies depending on issue, no more than 10 business days)

If action cannot be taken by the subject of the issue investigation to fully remedy the issue within the specified number of business days, the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office will suspend membership and Data Connectors related to the subject of the investigation until a plan of action is accepted and agreed upon.

The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** may engage legal counsel or law enforcement as necessary to protect the trust network within the OAEBUDT.

Issue Resolution

The OAEBUDT-IDS aims to support and work in good faith with **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** as they address issues that are raised. However, if evidence is found that provided data was intentionally misrepresented, or that actions were taken in direct conflict with the [OAEBUDT Community Limitations on the Use of Data Accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS](#), the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** reserves the right to hold parties accountable. (See [Participant Accountability Section](#))

Issue Resolution Process

Data Retraction, Correction, or Modifications

Data Providers will be able to retract, correct, or otherwise modify usage Data Connectors connected to the OAEBUDT-IDS. If adjustments are made to a Data Connector by a **Data Provider**, relevant [disclosures](#) about the usage data must be updated as soon as is reasonable to make transparent to **Data Recipients** a description of changes made. Changes to data provenance must be recorded and made available to **Data Recipients** via the OAEBUDT-IDS.

Remedies to Maintain Trust within IDS Network

Depending on the severity of the harm caused by the reported issue, accountability measures could include:

- Temporary pause to data exchange via the OAEBUDT-IDS to or from the participating organization in question, including IP address blocking,
- OAEBUDT Member Communications, such as an OAEBUDT-IDS notice to **Data Recipients** reflecting an active investigation, or an OAEBUDT network-wide communication regarding the issue,
- Legal action and liability, and
- Expulsion from the OAEBUDT trust network and OAEBUDT-IDS without financial refund or recourse

To support **Data Providers** and **Data Recipients** who may inadvertently or unintentionally cause an issue, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** may resolve an issue with or without a warning being noted on their member record.

The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** reserves all rights to address intentional, malicious, or other repeat actions that harm the OAEBUDT-IDS Participants on behalf of the OAEBUDT trust network. This includes taking action to temporarily or permanently disable Data Connectors, moving a member into probationary standing from good standing, and terminating a participant’s membership in the Data Trust.

Trust Protection Mechanisms

Part V. OAEBUDT-IDS Governance Mechanisms

Data Trust Coordinating Office as IDS Support Organization

Per the IDSA, an IDS support organization is, “Responsible for maintaining the rule book, supporting its application by coordinating key processes and governance of internal structures and interfaces to other parties.”¹⁷ The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** serves as the IDS Support Organization for the OAEBUDT-IDS, under the legal and fiscal administration of OPERAS-AIBSL as the effort’s fiscal sponsor and the strategic direction of its Board of Trustees.

To foster trust through machine-actionable data governance, processing, and transit, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will enforce policies and participation rules for the OAEBUDT-IDS. In such a “secretariat” capacity, a small staff will support governance, community engagement, and issue investigation functions in partnership with OPERAS-AIBSL, which acts as fiscal and legal sponsor for the OAEBUDT-IDS and thereby manages accounting and legal agreements related to OAEBUDT participation. The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** is staffed by individuals around the world, including but not limited to an Executive Director (based in the US in 2024), and a Community Manager (based in Switzerland in 2024). Additional staff will join the team as the OAEBUDT-IDS network grows.

Community Governance of the OAEBUDT-IDS

Board of Trustees and Board Committees

Members of the book publishing, discovery, and research ecosystem directly participate in the governance of the OAEBUDT through a Board of Trustees, board committees, and research project advisory boards. Such involvement helps the OAEBUDT-IDS to be transparent, inclusive, stakeholder governed and responsive to diverse stakeholder perspectives. The **OAEBUDT Board of Trustees** aims to provide independent governance to the OAEBUDT-IDS and **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office**. Trustees are expected to ensure that the OAEBUDT is neutral in its operations, and not reliant or biased toward any one type of **Data Provider** or **Data Recipient**.

Trustees serve in their personal capacities as subject matter experts, not as organizational representatives. All governance positions are on an at-will, volunteer basis and are unpaid. Individuals participating in the OAEBUDT-IDS community governance bodies agree to abide by the OAEBUDT’s Guiding Principles for OA Book Usage Data Services¹⁸ and the policies laid out in the OA Book Usage Data Trust’s Board Policy Book¹⁹. Trustees, committee members and staff disclose potential conflicts of interest in line with a Disclosure and Conflict of Interest Policy²⁰.

The OAEBUDT Board of Trustees provides strategy and oversight to the OAEBUDT and its OAEBUDT-IDS pursuant to its governance guidelines²¹, guiding principles, and Board Policy Book. It supervises the OAEBUDT Executive Director (ED) in conjunction with the Executive Director’s Organizational Host. The

¹⁷ https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-White-Paper-IDSARule-Book.pdf Pg 7.

¹⁸ <https://www.oabookusage.org/principles>

¹⁹

²⁰

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1o2d2RC5cL31Xr_5Uh_WZragSLJ7KikExhrkHdF0oIGQ/edit?usp=sharing

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/5703745>

Board of Trustees oversees the overall OAEBUDT budget in conjunction with project and programmatic fiscal sponsors which maintain fiscal controls and oversight. Trustees are elected for 3-year terms and serve as ambassadors of the OAEBUDT effort to the broader community through service on related research project advisory boards and board committees. A list of acting Trustees and committees is maintained on the OAEBUDT website.²²

Chartered board committees advance the work of the OAEBUDT. Chaired by Trustees, each committee allows individuals in the book publishing, discovery, and library professions to serve alongside existing Trustees and inform the work of the OAEBUDT in single year terms.²³ Those interested in committee service are encouraged to gain additional information and indicate their interest through the OAEBUDT website.

Advisory Bodies and Community Engagement

Stakeholders may serve on Project Advisory Boards alongside diverse teams of Principal Investigators for OAEBUDT-IDS related research and development (R&D) efforts, such as those listed on the OAEBUDT website.²⁴ The **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** also facilitates communities of interest, focus groups, workshops and public consultations to inform the overall development of the OAEBUDT-IDS.

Fiscal, Administrative, and Legal Sponsorship of the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office

To reduce administrative overhead through economies of scale, the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** is situated within a host organization. In 2023, the OAEBUDT Board of Trustees selected OPERAS-AIBSL, an international not-for-profit organization headquartered in Brussels, Belgium, to act as the fiscal, administrative, and legal sponsor for the OAEBUDT-IDS. OPERAS-AIBSL designees execute contracts and agreements on behalf of the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** and Board of Trustees with OAEBUDT-IDS participants, service providers, members, and supporters.

OAEBUDT-IDS Research Project Sponsorship

In recognition of the OAEBUDT's diverse community of researchers engaging in research and development projects related to the OAEBUDT-IDS, the **OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office** recognizes that research projects may be managed and sponsored by institutions other than OPERAS-AIBSL. Coordination with OPERAS-AIBSL is required if a project uses the OAEBUDT brand, staff, governance bodies, or infrastructure.

²² <https://www.oabookusage.org/governance>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8320009>

²⁴ See the <https://www.oabookusage.org/> Project History section

Part VI. Administration by the OAEBUDT-IDS Coordinating Office

Policy Administration

As a neutral data intermediary, the **OAEBUDT Coordinating Office** will equally apply rules and processes to all types of **Data Recipients** in accordance with local laws and regulations. Made up of a minimal staff, the Coordinating office will work to support interoperability and existing standards (e.g. COUNTER) while being supportive of emerging, related standards efforts. The Coordinating Office will enforce member compliance with the rules on (data) provenance, stewardship, and licensing as described in this rulebook and related contractual agreements.

Back-Office Administration

The OAEBUDT Coordinating Office, in conjunction with its fiscal sponsor, will support the functions of the OAEBUDT-IDS, by providing communications and information management infrastructures. This includes the OAEBUDT's website, calendars, and file systems, platforms to cultivate and manage member, grant, and sponsor agreements, and communications infrastructure to support community governance.

Financial Administration

Costs related to the management and provision of the OAEBUDT-IDS' technical and legal mechanisms will be shared across the participants of the OAEBUDT trust network. Cost-recovery mechanisms are under development. In line with the OAEBUDT trust network's principles, such mechanisms will allow for fair, inclusive pricing. Tiered and consortial memberships are anticipated, as are research and development grants, sponsorships, and scalable API-usage feeds. Community consultations and OAEBUDT Governance work through 2024 will inform cost-recovery oriented fee structures to ensure a sustainable, scalable financial foundation for this global, not-for-profit infrastructure.

Membership Administration

Status as an *Active Member in Good Standing* in the **OAEBUDT** is required to establish Data Connectors and/or exchange data via Data Connectors as a **Data Provider** or **Data Recipient** in the OAEBUDT-IDS. Membership status within the OAEBUDT is contingent upon compliance with the [terms](#) that accompany OAEBUDT-IDS participation.

OAEBUDT membership types, fees, and processes are overseen by the OAEBUDT Board of Trustees and administered by the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office and OPERAS-AISBL as the OAEBUDT fiscal sponsor.

Membership Types {section to be developed in 2024}

Data Providers

Data Recipients

Joint Data Provider/Recipients

Membership Fee Structure { to be developed in 2024}

Tiered, consortia possible, more details TBD

Membership Processes { to be developed in 2024}

Refer to a website page describing onboarding / membership process, key contacts, timelines. Incl. process of evaluation/certification related to requirements above.

Membership Payment Periods

To reduce administrative overhead, OAEBUDT Membership fees will be assessed on an annual basis. Members joining after the annual 30 day membership processing period will be able to join on a pro-rata rate for the remainder of the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office's budgetary year.

Late Membership Payment

If an OAEBUDT membership contract is executed but fees remain unpaid after 12 months, the late organization will have 30 days to pay for both the prior and upcoming year of membership. If no payment is received within 30 days of the 12 month overdue period, the organization will no longer be a member in good standing and all of their Data Connectors will be suspended on day 31.

Active Membership / Membership in Good Standing Definition { to be developed in 2024}

{note ongoing responsibility for the data and responsiveness to issue investigation/resolution process' active status required for data exchange}}

Suspension of Membership { to be developed in 2024}

As specified under the [Accountability Mechanisms section](#) of this rulebook, an OAEBUDT Member must take action if notified by the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office of a reported issue pertaining to their organizational participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS. Depending on the nature and severity of the issue, and the risk of harm to OAEBUDT participants, a member's status and Data Connectors may be temporarily suspended during an investigation.

Suspension of membership results in an OAEBUDT Member's loss of the following privileges:

- {to be defined in 2024 by the Membership Sustainability Committee / BoT}

OAEBUDT Expulsion and Immediate Membership Cancellation

As specified in the [Accountability Mechanisms section](#) of this rulebook, an OAEBUDT Member that does not comply with OAEBUDT-IDS terms may be expelled from the OAEBUDT as a result of the issue notification, investigation, and resolution process. Membership cancellation caused by OAEBUDT expulsion will not result in any refund of fees paid.

Withdrawal/Departure from OAEBUDT Network { to be developed in 2024}

{note at will participation, ability to withdraw and leave, what happens to the Data Connectors, outstanding membership payments/pledges, notification to other OAEBUDT participants}

Sponsorship and/or Donation Administration { to be developed in 2024}

Data Trust Supporters Definition, Modes of engagement

Administrative Process: onboarding as a donor/sponsor, Administration provided by OPERAS-AIBSL as OAEBUDT-IDS Fiscal Sponsor.

Grant Administration { to be developed in 2024}

...

OAEBUDT-IDS Technical Service Provider Contract Administration (section to be written after technical pilot)**Selection / Renewal Process****Service Level Agreements****OAEBUDT-IDS Onboarding (section to be written after technical pilot)****Usage Data Providers**

{Define role, what must be prepared to connect to the IDS-network, and the requirements that must be met pre-connection (i.e. signed agreements, data prep, etc.)

Contracts and Agreements (Legal Review and Preparation)

- Standard Contractual Clauses

- Data Licensing options

Technical Data Preparation:

- Usage data description / preparation

To establish that an organization will be transparent about the usage data it makes available to others, a Data Provider must provide required information when configuring the OAEBUDT-IDS Data Connector:

1. describe the process by which the usage data was created,
2. provide a description of usage data provenance, to allow others to understand who was involved in the creation and processing of usage data prior to it being made available to the OA Book Usage Data Trust,
3. provide metadata for the usage data that it believes to be accurate, including at a minimum: {list TBD}, and
4. describe all transformations or processing conducted on the usage data prior to making it available through the Data Trust (noting algorithms, code, or standards that were applied where applicable, and whether such algorithms, code or standards are proprietary or available for open review).

This information will be requested of Data Providers through the IDS platform

- Systems security assessment
 - Evaluation / Certification process
 - IDS Readiness to Participate Certification
 - How certification evaluators are selected and approved
 - Evaluation process for OAEBUDT participant applicants

Usage Data Recipients**Contracts and Agreements (Legal Review and Preparation)**

- Standard Contractual Clauses

Data Licensing options

Technical Data Preparation:

Usage data description / preparation

o

Process for Dual data provider / recipients

OAEBUDT-IDS Offboarding (section to be written after technical pilot)

SECTION III | OAEBUDT-IDS TECHNICAL OVERVIEW (To Be Developed in 2024)

The OAEBUDT-IDS aims to provide a streamlined, easy-to-use mechanism for scholarly communications usage Data Providers and Data Recipients to exchange usage data in a way that is trusted and as controlled as necessary. This section outlines the standards and technical systems that make up the OAEBUDT-IDS infrastructure,

{API documentation and other technical documentation regarding Data Recipient access to data may be added or referenced after the technical pilot}

Part I. Standards supporting the OAEBUDT-IDS Network Infrastructure

{Intro note re: neutrality as data intermediary, aim to be certifiable data space, importance of IDS standard for cross-industry data exchange interoperability} Note much is defined by the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (RAM) & Certification Requirements

International Data Space Standards

IDS Reference Architecture Model

IDS Certification Criteria

Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS)

Cybersecurity Standards

Book Industry Standards

Scholarly Communications Standards

Part II - Technical Services Supporting the OAEBUDT-IDS

The essential IDS Services that will be provided via the OAEBUDT-IDS Network will follow the neutral IDS core data exchange services²⁵, defined in emerging Industry Data Space standards as business roles²⁶. They will include the following:

Identity Provider

OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose

In order to build trust between the Data Providers and Data Recipients, a workflow is needed to support access control related processes based on identities of the organisations participating in the data space. Identity and Access Management (IAM) practices will be required to verify organizational affiliation and approve individual rules-based access.

IDS-RAM Definition

The IDSA defines an *Identity Provider* as a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) capable of asserting user and organizational identities with associated security and trust levels.

OAEBUDT-IDS Identity Service Provider

{to be filled in after Gap Analysis and Data Model Projects Complete - placeholder text below}

As of {date} the organization providing the *Identity Service* for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem is {service provider name}. {service provider name} is providing this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}.

Metadata Broker

OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose

To foster the discovery, interpretation, and interoperability of exchanged book usage data, Data Providers must describe their usage data feeds in a uniform, machine readable way when connecting to the OAEBUDT-IDS. The OAEBUDT-IDS interface will prompt Data Providers to describe the data and its provenance, data quality and trust indicators ([see section below](#)). The storage, access, and retrieval of such metadata values pertaining to the OAEBUDT IDS data feeds will be managed by a metadata broker service provider for the OAEBUDT.

IDS-RAM Definition

The IDSA defines this Metadata Broker role as an index service of metadata shared by data connectors to facilitate link-based discovery of data sources.²⁷ Within the OAEBUDT-IDS environment the metadata broker(s) would index and/or share metadata specific to the book publishing and discovery industries.

OAEBUDT-IDS Metadata Broker Service Provider

²⁵ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/use/ids-components/>

²⁶ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0/blob/main/documentation/3_Layers_of_the_Reference_Architecture_Model/3_1_Business_Layer/3_1_1_Roles_in_the_IDS.md#business-roles-in-the-international-data-space

²⁷ Bader, Sebastian. (2020). Specification: IDS Meta Data Broker (1.0). Pgs 11-12. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675076>

{to be filled in after Gap Analysis and Data Model Projects Complete - placeholder text below}

As of {date} the organization providing the Metadata Broker service for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem is {service provider name}. {service provider name} is providing this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}

Data Clearinghouse**OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose**

The Clearinghouse provides for an accounting of data exchange and transformation (clearing) functions a) prior to data exchange (verifying usage policies, data access financial conditions, and logging transaction against a data sharing agreement, b) during active data exchange (logging of sharing action, tracing data provenance, auditing, reporting and if applicable invoicing based on data transactions, and c) after data exchange (investigation and enforcement of usage policy).²⁸

IDS-RAM Definition

The IDSA defines the *Data Clearinghouse* as an intermediary that provides clearing and settlement services for all financial and data exchange transactions²⁹. In the IDS-RAM, clearing activities are separated from any data brokerage services, since these activities are technically different. However as already stated above, a single organization may play multiple roles in the IDS.

OAEBUDT-IDS Data Clearinghouse Service Provider**{to be filled in after Gap Analysis and Data Model Projects Complete - placeholder text below}**

As of {date} the organization providing the *Data Clearinghouse* service for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem is {service provider name}. {service provider name} is providing this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}

IDS App Store**OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose**

To enhance discovery and provide access to trusted applications for OAEBUDT data processing, an App Store securely hosts and provisions code for the IDS (aka Apps) to transform, aggregate, or otherwise process OA Book Usage data in transit.

IDS-RAM Definition

According to the IDSA, the business role of the App Store is to distribute data apps. In contrast to the Service Provider, the algorithm is not executed in the platform of the App Store, but provided for download to the IDS connector of the App Consumer. App Consumer and App Owner may be different, if the owner acquires (purchases) an app, but lets it be distributed to Service Provider. The App Store role typically comprises the basic roles of the App Broker and App Provider.

OAEBUDT-IDS App Store Provider

²⁸ Bastiaansen, Dr. ir. Harrie, Bramm, Georg, Ceballos, Juan, Gall, Mark, & Kolenstart, Maarten. (2020). Specification: IDS Clearing House (1.0). Pgs 7-8. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675765>

²⁹ IDS Clearing House Specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.522633>

{to be filled in after Gap Analysis and Data Model Projects Complete - placeholder text below}

As of {date} the organization providing the *App Store* service for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem is {service provider name}. {service provider name} is providing this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}

IDS Vocabularies and Persistent Identifiers Providers**OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose**

To enhance discovery and provide access to trusted applications for OAEBUDT data processing, an App Store securely hosts and provisions code for the IDS (aka Apps) to transform, aggregate, or otherwise process OA Book Usage data in transit.

IDS-RAM Definition

According to the IDSA, the business role of the App Store is to distribute data apps. In contrary to the Service Provider, the algorithm is not executed in the platform of the App Store, but provided for download to the IDS connector of the App Consumer. App Consumer and App Owner may be different, if the owner acquires (purchases) an app, but lets it be distributed to Service Provider. The App Store role typically comprises the basic roles of the App Broker and App Provider.

OAEBUDT-IDS Vocabularies and Persistent Identifiers Provider**{to be filled in after Gap Analysis and Data Model Projects Complete - placeholder text below}**

As of {date} the organization providing the *App Store* service for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem is {service provider name}. {service provider name} is providing this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}

Usage Data Connectors**OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose**

To facilitate automated, rules based data access in a way that is as open as possible but as controlled as necessary, the OAEBUDT-IDS provides {describe connector code} through which Data Providers and Data Recipients make their data available to the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem.

IDS-RAM Definition

The IDSA defines Usage Data Connectors as technical core components required for a participant to join the International Data Spaces

OAEBUDT-IDS Usage Data Connector Service Provider

Data Providers and Data Recipients will use *Usage Data Connectors* for the OAEBUDT-IDS ecosystem {service provider name} will manage the data connected to this service for the OAEBUDT-IDS according to published terms and conditions {cited here}. For providing this service, {service provider} is remunerated through {remuneration details to reflect sustainability}. To ensure continuity of the OAEBUDT-IDS, {Service provider} must...{insert terms to assure SLA/continuity}

IDS Evaluation Provider**OAEBUDT-IDS Purpose**

To establish trust among {...}, {organization types} must {...} when connecting to the OAEBUDT-IDS. {OAEBUDT entity} will evaluate {...} according to {...}, thereby allowing {...}

IDS-RAM Definition

The IDSA defines the *Evaluation Provider* role as...

OAEBUDT-IDS Evaluation Service Provider**IDS Certification Body**

Within the IDS-RAM, a *Certification Body* role is defined for the party that's responsible for managing the membership and identity verification (i.e. certification) of the participants and service level agreements with the core technical components, to maintain an operational IDS.

Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service

IDS Service Provider:

Service Level Agreement (SLA) Term:

SLA Scope:

Participant Information Service

SECTION IV | OAEBUDT-IDS Wide Service Level Agreements {Develop after technical pilot}

Section IV: This section defines Service Level Agreement (SLA) terms for the OAEBUDT-IDS technical services.

Intro re: Commitments that can be communicated to Data Providers and Data Recipients re: uptime, security, etc.

OAEBUDT-IDS Network Maintenance

OAEBUDT-IDS RAM Change Management / Version Management

Need: Meet IDS Standards for Certification as an IDS
Versioning

Release and Adoption Policy

OAEBUDT-IDS Data Connectors

SECTION V | Legal Agreements and Contractual Clauses (section to be inserted mid/late 2024)

Note: derived from principles within this rulebook, they exist in addition to data licenses between any data providers and data recipient's independent of the OAEBUDT

OA Book Usage Data Trust Data Use Agreement

OA Book Usage Data Trust Data Transfer Agreement

OA Book Usage Data Trust Data Trust Participation Agreement

SECTION VI | Appendix

Related Document References

OAEBUDT One-pager³⁰

OA Book Usage Data Trust Frequently Asked Questions³¹

Rulebook Workshop Discussion Paper | Building an International Data Space for OA Book Usage³²

OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report³³

Design Principles for International Data Spaces³⁴

Specification: IDS Metadata Broker³⁵

Specification: IDS Clearing House³⁶

Data Connector Report³⁷

IDS Certification Explained³⁸

Criteria Catalogue: Components Broker³⁹

Criteria Catalogue: Operational Environments⁴⁰

OAEBUDT-IDS Data Catalogue/Data Dictionary {Forthcoming - to be developed in technical pilot}

OAEBUDT-IDS Data Model {Forthcoming - to be developed in technical pilot}

OAEBUDT-IDS Use Cases

³⁰ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1yVDx7xl1GxrHGbt81sLuS962uHjo-LR/view>

³¹

³² Drummond, C. (2023). Rulebook Workshop Discussion Paper | Building an International Data Space for OA Book Usage. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8345034>

³³ Clarke, M., & Ricci, L. (2021). OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

³⁴ Nagel, L., & Lycklama, D. (2021). Design Principles for Data Spaces - Position Paper (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>

³⁵ Bader, S. (2020). Specification: IDS Meta Data Broker (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675076>

³⁶ Bastiaansen, D. ir H., Bramm, G., Ceballos, J., Gall, M., & Kolenstart, M. (2020). Specification: IDS Clearing House (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675765>

³⁷ Giussani, G., Steinbuss, S., Holesch, M., & Gras, N. (2024). Data Connector Report (11.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10591027>

³⁸ Steinbuss, S., Menz, N., Resetko, A., & Winkel, J. (2019). IDS Certification explained (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675945>

³⁹ Bader, S. (2020). Criteria Catalogue: Components – Broker (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675735>

⁴⁰ Steinbuss, S., Menz, N., & Resetko, A. (2020). Criteria Catalogue: Operational Environments (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675802>

Glossary

{To be developed/ revised in technical pilot}

- ❖ Data Connector: The mechanism by which an organization connects their data flows to the technical IDS ecosystem
- ❖ Data Owner: The entity with the legal ability to authorize uses of a given data flow enabled through a data connector
- ❖ Data Provider: The entity that makes data available to others through a data connector
- ❖ Data Recipient: The entity that receives and uses data through the IDS data connectors
- ❖ International Data Space (IDS): a controlled data exchange ecosystem developed to be compliant with the IDS-Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM)
- ❖ OAEBUDT: Open Access Book Usage Data Trust
- ❖ OAEBUDT Coordinating Office: The administrative function of the Open Access Book Usage Data Trust effort, which manages legal, financial, and contractual processes for the technical system and membership administration
- ❖ OAEBUDT-IDS: Open Access Usage Data Trust International Data Space - the technical data space infrastructure through which data space participants securely exchange data in a controlled fashion
- ❖ OAEBUDT Member: a member of the Open Access Usage Data Trust effort that with a fully executed and paid membership agreement
- ❖ OAEBUDT-IDS Participant: A legal organization with an executed agreement with the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office as one of the roles in the OAEBUDT-IDS, including but not limited to: member, sponsor, Data Provider, Data Recipient, Service Provider
- ❖ Accuracy: Usage Data “Accuracy” is defined as...
- ❖ Consent: In alignment with the GDPR, “Consent” is defined as...
- ❖ Metadata: “Metadata” is defined as...